

IMPORTANCE OF GRATITUDE EXPRESSIONS ON SOCIAL MEDIA AND BUSINESS COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: *The present article investigates the variety forms of gratitude expressions utilized in main types of social networks that are considered as powerful communication channels. This paper also discusses gratitude strategies in Business Communication which are often neglected by employees. Gratitude has an impact on more than just internal interactions between coworkers and management. They can also build the trust between partners or investors, as well as the relationship between the business and its customers.*

Key Words : *Social networking accounts, advancement in technology, commercial activity , work performance, emoticons*

Introduction

Since full writing- systems have been invented in four different civilization, they were used for different purposes in different countries. In general, scholars agree that initial type of writing firstly appeared in Mesopotamia as a pictorial signs which characterize and represent the sounds of Sumerian about 5,500BC years ago. The last datable document in this language is an astronomical text. New discoveries of writing can be found in Egypt close to Mesopotamia around 3250BC. They have characteristics that are similar to hieroglyphic forms that are utilized in religious and royal ceremonies. The first evidence of writing in China were discovered near Beijing in the form of “Oracle Bones”, containing 4500 different symbols many of which can be identified as the ancestors of Chinese characters still in use today. When it comes to Maya, Mixtecs and Aztecs, they used two types of writing systems, namely open and closed. Open systems were methods of recording texts that were unrelated to the grammatical and phonological patterns of individual languages. They served as mnemonic techniques, directing readers through text narratives without relying on the audience's language knowledge. These were common among the Aztecs and other central Mexican populations. Closed

systems were linked to specific language sounds and grammatical patterns. These were aimed for certain linguistic communities and functioned similarly to modern writing. These closed systems can be seen among the Maya. Most of the scholars agree that these are proto-writing and picture writing systems which include simplified pictures or glyphs which represent objects and concepts, as well as the ideographic which directly represent abstract symbols as an idea or concept. There have been many changes since the evolution of writing until the discovery of present-day alphabets.

Over the last 20 years, technological advancement affected almost every aspect of our life, even the way people use the internet. Invention of social networking sites, especially Facebook, Twitter and YouTube united billions of people across the Globe. When the emoji firstly invented by Shigetaka Kurita, he brought back us to the period of emergence of writing-system. Because the emoji is a pictographic writing tradition that dates back millennia to Egyptian hieroglyphics and Japanese ideograms. Using Emoji on Apple and Google platforms internationally started in 2000s. Unicode adopted the thumbs up emoji in 2010 and this was the first step toward emojis becoming recognized as a language. The "Face with Tears" (also known as the laugh-cry emoji) was so popular that the Oxford Dictionary declared it a word in 2015. The main aim of this paper is to show gratitude on social media and importance of gratitude in business communication and workplace.

Gratitude expressions in Social Media Platforms

As has been stated numerous times (Rubin 1983, Eisenstein & Bodman 1986, 1993, Bodman & Eisenstein 1988, Wolfson 1989, Aston 1995), the term thank you can perform a variety of tasks in addition to thanking. As with many politeness conventions, however, there appears to be a large degree of cross-cultural variations in the use and realization of thanking, so that saying 'thank you' is a problem not only for the first but also for the second language learner, who needs to learn when and how to thank in the target culture[1]. It is worth mentioning that sharing gratitude through social networking sites could improve overall well-being of young people. Analyzing and investigating gratitude on social networks is a brand new research in the scientific discipline. There are a number of ways to share gratitude online. Currently, most of the networking sites have thank you pages where users get to immediately after they have completed desired action on the site. This might be anything as simple as signing up for a newsletter, getting free e-book, making a purchase, or signing up for a webinar. Regardless of the activity taken, the user should be directed to the

thank you page as soon as possible after completing it. A proper thank you page is a technique to strengthen client relationships and an opportunity to link with other sites, generate leads, boost revenue, and recruit clients.

In addition to that, nowadays nearly every social media platform offer a referral bonus to show gratitude for their subscribers. Dropbox became a popular cloud storage provider due to this strategy. The aim is to express gratitude to the users for suggesting the product to a friend who purchases it. Dropbox, for example, offered additional storage for free if you suggest a friend who purchases a Dropbox subscription.

Another way to express gratitude online is to provide customer with promo codes as a gift. It will be a pleasant surprise for clients who utilize promotional codes until they expire. Replying to comments is an alternative way to show gratitude and appreciation. When someone comments on one of the famous organization's social media postings, SM managers take advantage of the chance to continue the conversation and express gratitude for following page. They respond to reviews, direct messages, and any other activity on one's social media page as promptly as possible. In this case, the following template responses of gratitude are mostly utilized:

"Thank you so much for reaching out. If you send us a direct message with your contact information, we will be in touch as soon as possible."

"Your purchase is already helping make a difference for our program-Thank You"

"Thank you so much for taking the time to share your review".

When thanking other businesses with social media profiles (such as venues or business sponsors), one will make sure to tag them on Facebook as an appreciation by first inputting the "@" symbol and then the page's name. A dropdown menu will appear, and they can then select the page they want to include in their post from the list. Apart from those mentioned above, there is also exclusive way of sharing gratitude on the net. Hosting a giveaway is an excellent way to show thanks to followers. For instance , giving away a special gift on Instagram is an effective strategy to reach thousands of potential new followers and help partners or sponsors to feature their new product simultaneously.

During Coronavirus pandemic, Twitter launched an emoji for users for expressing gratitude. With the words, such as #thankfulness, #gratitude appeared a new emoji in different languages on this platform. From February to March in 2020, there have been over 265 million tweets worldwide expressing gratitude and thanks.

The most frequently used emoji to convey positive feelings, love, happiness and gratitude is a classic smiley with a modest smile, rosy cheeks, and soft, closed eyes, in yellow color according to Emojipedia. It is similar to “Smiling face with smiling eyes” which has no eyebrows but with a broader smile and smiling eyes. A yellow face smiling with open hands, as if giving a hug is used to express thankfulness and love. Emoticon which is widely used in conversations to say thanks and gratitude is “folded hands”, meaning please or thank you in Japanese culture.

Gratitude in the workplace

The word gratitude and business are rarely used together in a sentence. But gratitude may play an important role in establishing a positive corporate culture and a productive workplace. According to recent research undertaken by the John Templeton Foundation, the workplace is the least probable venue for Americans to express thankfulness. Although 93 percent of respondents thought that a grateful boss is more likely to succeed, and nearly all agreed that a simple “thank you” at work gave a feeling of appreciation, just 10 percent were genuinely skip gratitude. The majority of respondents, or 60%, have never expressed thanks at work or have only done once a year. Interestingly, an expression of gratitude costs nothing and it only requires attention and time.

It is worth noting that positive behaviors and a grateful culture must begin at the top. A simple thank you from the boss might go a long way. CEO of Campbell's soups once sent 30,000 handwritten thank you notes to his staff. It was part of establishing an appreciation culture throughout the organization. Alternate way of expressing gratitude at work is to send letters or e-mails. A template for a thank you and appreciation e-mail or letter are readily available online to express gratitude to sponsor or director at work.

Dear Mr. Brown

On behalf of the Advertisement company management, I would like to extend our appreciation for the amazing work done by you in referring a job vacancy candidate and being a good leader.

Your diligence, self-motivation and passion for your role within the Advertisement company are really admirable.

We know the amount of effort that you put into your work and we want to assure you that your efforts are significantly appreciated.

Our sincere thanks. We are very lucky to have you!

Kindest regards,

Ashley Olson, executive director

Leaders who practice value-centered leadership will discover that being grateful has numerous benefits for themselves and their companies, including the opportunity to boost goodwill and citizenship behavior. The benefits of gratitude-enhancing interventions will most likely aid in the development of value-centered leaders. This should apply to both leaders who possess and exhibit appreciation as a character strength and those who may not be as strong in this area but wish to develop in expressing thanks.

Appreciation research (conducted primarily outside of organizational contexts) shows that those who express gratitude reap numerous benefits. Applied researchers share some tried-and-true methods for helping us become more thankful.

Conclusion

Concluding the paper one can come to conclusion that sharing gratitude on online community among media users may vary in accordance with intended purpose, style preferences, and modern perspectives and features of gratitude and appreciation. While being grateful in the workplace will have a positive impact to maintain and improve productivity and performance of both employees and employers at work. However, it is worth mentioning that a number of issues of this scientific discipline are still remaining disputable.

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